

Momentum Wavefunction of a Particle in a Box

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The momentum wavefunction f_p of a particle in a box (with infinite potential walls) has been described (1) (2) in terms of many plane waves (i.e. many f_p 's) even though the energy $E = (\hbar k)^2 / 2m$ expresses only one k . Thus, the energy E appears to be an average. It seems one may have a plane wave $\exp(ipx)$ which collides inelastically with the wall and changes to $\exp(-ipx)$ etc.; on average energy is conserved. In (1) and (2), the spatial wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ is obtained by solving the time-independent Schrodinger equation, and f_p from taking the Fourier transform of $W(x)$. These are strictly math procedures it seems. In a previous note (3), the time independent Schrodinger equation is written with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ both expressed in terms of Fourier transforms. This lead to an equation for each p of the form:

$$\sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_k = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \quad ((1)).$$

In such a case, $V(x)$ exists throughout x . For the case of an infinite wall, there is still a potential, but only at the end walls. In this note, we suggest ((1)) may be used to obtain f_p without taking the Fourier transform of $W(x)$ or solving for V_k . This approach also shows cycling is involved, even for a particle in a box. The cycling occurs at the walls.

Particle in a Box

In general, the time-independent Schrodinger equation is solved for a particle in a box to obtain $W(x)$, the spatial wavefunction. The potential exists only at the boundaries, so the differential equation has a zero $V(x)$ for other x values. Once $W(x)$ is found, f_p may be obtained using:

$$F_p = \int dx W(x) \exp(-ipx).$$

In (1) the following results are presented. (In (2), a factor $\exp(ikx_c)$ where x_c is the center of the potential becomes 1 if the $x_c=0$. We use that choice.

$$W_n(x) = 1/\sqrt{a} \sin[\pi n/2a (x-a)] \text{ for } |x| < a \text{ and } W_n(x) = 0 \text{ elsewhere}$$

Here $W_n(x)$ has the form of a sin or cos depending on n using $x_c=0$ as the center.

$$f_p = \sqrt{\pi n^2 / a^3} \sin(ap - \pi n/2) / [2m(p^2/2m - E)]$$

f_p also changes from cos to sin as one changes from one n to another.

Cycling Approach

In a previous note, it was suggested plane waves scatter from a potential from one p into another in a cycling manner to form a resonance. Each f_p plane wave is created by other plane waves f_k combining with V_j (the Fourier transform of V) and each f_p in turn combines with V_j to form other f_l 's. Thus, a cycling occurs, but each f_p cycles with the same frequency, namely E . To see this, we showed that $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ can be written as Fourier series and the time-independent Schrodinger equation written as:

$$\sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \quad ((2))$$

The Sum can also be thought of as a dot product. It seems that ((2)) is suggestive of the form of the momentum wavefunction for a particle in a box. Usually, $V(x)$ has a value for a range of x , but for the box, there is only a potential at $x=a$ and $x=-a$. In addition, E the average energy, usually incorporates average kinetic energy and average potential energy from $V(x)$. Here E is of the form $(\hbar k)^2 / 2m$ with $\hbar k(n) = 6.28 n/2a$. Thus, k is an average rms p value. A certain $p=k(n)$ and one does not want the right hand side of ((2)) to be 0 or infinite. For different n values, the p in question changes. To satisfy this constraint, one may suggest:

$$f_p = g(p) / (E - p^2/2m) \quad ((3))$$

Next, one must determine $g(p)$. For the box potential, scattering occurs only at the walls $x=a$ or $x=-a$. For a free particle, the wavefunction is $\exp(ikx)$ or $\exp(-ikx)$. One may consider scattering with a phase of 1 or -1 at each p level to have a real wavefunction, but x should be evaluated at a or $-a$. This seems to suggest a form of $\cos(pa)$ or $\sin(pa)$ for $g(p)$. This would give a relative weight for different p 's i.e. $f_{p1}/f_{p2} = (E - p_2^2/2m) \cos(p_1 a) / [\cos(p_2 a) (E - p_1^2/2m)]$. For $|x| < a$, there are no interactions and so the relative weight should not depend on other x values. Thus, it seems one may postulate a form for the momentum wavefunction f_p without explicitly calculating V_j (the Fourier transform of $V(x)$) and without calculating the Fourier transform of $W(x)$. One may suggest:

$$f_{p,n} = C_n [\cos(pa) \text{ or } \sin(pa) \text{ depending on } n] / (E_n - p^2/2m) \quad ((4))$$

This seems to give the same result as in (1),(2). The reason this approach is suggested is that f_p is not only a mathematical Fourier transform, but has physical meaning even at the f_p level. It is known that $P(p) = f_p^* f_p$, but f_p is not simply the square root of probability. It appears in conditional probabilities i.e.

$$P(p/x) = f_p \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad \text{and} \quad P(x/p) = W(x) \exp(-ipx) / f_p \quad ((5))$$

Thus, f_p is an important component of conditional probabilities even without being squared. Thus, we think one should be able to obtain it using physical arguments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest it may be possible to use an equation for each p obtained by substituting the Fourier transform for $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ into the Schrodinger equation:

$$\sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \quad ((2))$$

to obtain f_p for a particle in a box with infinite walls. In such a case, there is no $V(x)$ except at the box walls, but it is argued the same type of particle -potential scattering occurs at the walls as occurs in the case of $V(x)$ not zero. Thus, $V(x)=0$ except at the walls and $V(x)$ not zero can be treated in a similar manner. We argue for a $(E - p^2/2m)$ denominator to ensure the right hand side of ((2)) does not vanish if $p^2/2m=E$ and consider the remaining factor to be proportional to the weights of the different $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$ evaluated at $x=a$ or $x=-a$ because this is where the collisions occur. These weights established at the wall, hold throughout $|x|<a$.

References

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